

MECHANISMS TO PREVENT PROCRASTINATION IN YOUNG LEADERS

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Annotation: In this article, techniques for preventing procrastination in young leaders and scientific theoretical opinions about procrastination are presented.

Key words: Procrastination, skill, theoretical leader, post-industrial, coping, psychology.

This research cycle is devoted to the characteristics of the manifestation of the phenomenon of procrastination in innovative professions, the relevance of the topic is related to the increasing demands of the environment in which a modern person lives. It is primarily characterized by constant variability and high innovation. Scientific and technical progress has led to the formation of a post-industrial type of society, which is characterized by the rapid development of fields requiring science. Over the past 50 years, there have been changes in the nature of work. The development of information technologies leads to information overload and the innovative readiness of a person requires a lot of skills from young leaders.

In today's environment, the old principles of management cease to work for managing employees who organize most of the working time independently. In modern conditions, a person is very vulnerable to the effects of procrastination, which causes many physical and psychological health problems. In this regard, the issue of ways to overcome procrastination is very relevant (Leonova, Kuznetsova, 2007). In Western literature, the study of this problem continues in the direction of developing the concepts of procrastination coping and procrastination behavior (Leonova, 2004).

In Russian psychology, the ideas of overcoming procrastination situations and fighting against them develop in accordance with the psychology of experience and individual activity style (Bodrov, 2000, Krukova, 2004). Within the psychology of struggle, the phenomenon of procrastination can be understood as a self-regulatory failure (Steel, 2007), in which a person tends to "procrastinate" difficult and unpleasant actions. According to foreign researchers, 15-25% of people have a stable delay, and over time this level will increase among the population. Although some researchers believe that this phenomenon has always been characteristic of man, scientific analysis of the problems of this phenomenon has begun in the scientific literature, and questionnaires have been developed to study procrastination. Today, this topic has begun to attract the attention of local psychologists.

The novelty and theoretical importance of the presented research is due to the fact that currently the problems of procrastination in psychology are still poorly developed. It is presented as part of the study of its main issues. Thus, the study of the psychological mechanisms of laziness is related to delaying the event, the psychological components of laziness were examined, the subjective perception and evaluation of laziness was studied.

Studies of the causes of laziness have looked at biological and personal factors such as anxiety, motivational problems, volitional regulation problems, and self-esteem traits.

In the Western tradition, procrastination is distinguished as a phenomenon distinct from laziness. Researchers say that although procrastination and laziness share a number of common features, such as reluctance to act and lack of motivation, laziness should be classified only as one of the possible forms of "procrastination".

Another unique feature of our study is that the phenomenon of procrastination is examined in connection with different levels of prevention of procrastination in young leaders. Studies conducted abroad have shown that procrastination can be associated with high levels of stress and poor coping strategies, which affect a person's health and quality of life. However, the mechanisms of interaction of these factors are still not completely clear and require further study (Tice, Baumeister, 1997; Sirois, Pychyl, 2002).

It should also be noted that preventing the phenomenon of procrastination in young executives works as subjects in our study. Most of the research currently available is based on student materials. But recently, more and more information is emerging about the negative impact of this phenomenon on the work efficiency of professionals. Thus, procrastination has been found to lead to lost time, poor productivity, and increased stress levels in organizations' employees (Chu, Choi, 2005).

Research conducted by the large American consulting company "H&R Block" showed that in 2002, mistakes caused by procrastination in some way cost companies 473 million dollars. A number of studies point to the damage that "procrastination" causes to the politics and economy of countries (Steel, 2010).

In our work to study the phenomenon of procrastination, we tried to take into account all the facts we know and design a study that includes:

- ❖ Studying procrastination in young leaders;
- ❖ consideration of organizational (group) factors;
- ❖ taking into account the specific characteristics of the activity (the field of web development);
- ❖ taking into account the specific characteristics of stressful situations (acute and chronic stress);
- ❖ consideration of personal characteristics (motivational factors and voluntary regulation characteristics).

The issue of procrastination in the workplace is primarily related to the problem of employee motivation. Currently, in applied psychology, there are various methods of combating procrastination at the level of improving the skills of goal setting, planning and activity management. These methods can be found in the works of the most famous researchers of procrastination problems, among which T. Pychyl (2009), R. F. Baumeister, J. Tierney (2011), G. Rubin (2012) should be highlighted.

In addition to strategies for increasing personal efficiency, special management methods are used. One such method is the now very popular "constraint theory" of Dr. E. Goldratt (2006). This theory focuses on increasing the profits of organizations by eliminating existing problems (Goldratt, 2006). The method of project management is represented by the Critical Chain method proposed by E. Goldratt in 1997. The need to develop this method is due to the fact that only 44% of projects are completed on time, according to the StandishGroup. On average, projects occupy 222% of the allocated time and 189% of the planned budget. In the

Tos model, procrastination turns out to be one of the reasons why projects are not completed on time. The special planning method used in Tos allows the manager to avoid the impact of such delays on the project work (Goldratt, 2006).

Thus, studying the phenomenon of procrastination can help project managers better understand why there are delays in project tasks in terms of individual characteristics of employees and their current situation. In addition, it is important to focus the attention of managers on the consequences of improper organization of the work process in terms of mental and physical well-being of employees.

It is important to provide a detailed description of an ambiguous phenomenon such as procrastination, justifying the need to conduct a published study. As shown, procrastination is a very common form of behavioral regulation, the causes and mechanisms of which are not yet fully understood. Procrastination is common in the general population, but college students are most affected by it (Steel, 2007). It was found that 80-95% of students have experienced procrastination, about 75% consider themselves to be procrastinators, and about 50% constantly experience such a situation, which causes them serious problems. In the general population, 15-20% of adults are prone to procrastination (Harriott, Ferrari, 1996). It should be noted that about 95% of people who report procrastination describe it as harmful and wish to get rid of it.

Procrastination means putting off something unpleasant for a person until later. This term was introduced in 1971 by P. Rigenbach in the book "delay in human life". Interestingly, this work never existed. It was a joke about a book about never-ending procrastination. The first systematic analysis of the phenomenon was carried out in 1992 by N. Milgram. In his work, he assumed that procrastination as a social phenomenon arose due to the fact that modern human life in a post-industrial society is filled with many obligations and time constraints. J.Ferrari and his colleagues offered a similar explanation because this phenomenon has always existed, but only recently has it acquired negative connotations (Ferrari, Johnsonson, McCown, 1995).

The causes and mechanisms of procrastination are still being studied. There are many studies that show that the severity of this phenomenon is correlated with low self-esteem, lack of self-confidence, lack of self-control, high tendency to perfectionism, impulsivity, depression and anxiety.

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